

Work-related dimensions and job stress: the moderating effect of coping strategies

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Summary

The aim of this paper is to examine the moderating effect of coping strategies on the relationship between work-related dimensions (i.e., work routinization, role clarity, relationships with others, and promotional opportunity) and job stress. For the study a convenience sample of 385 white-collar employees full-time employed in various types of private sector organisations belong to different industries and ranked at different levels within the organisations responded. The factor analysis led to identify four broad coping strategies that individuals use, namely, individual positive coping, workplace initiatives, workplace informal support, and individual destructive coping. It was found that both individual positive coping and workplace initiatives moderate the relationship between “relationships with others” and job stress. However, none of the coping strategies have moderated the relationship between job stress and the other three work-related dimensions.

Key words

Job stress; coping strategies; work routinization; role clarity; promotional opportunity

Introduction

Stress may be encountered in virtually every key element in a particular job, yet, the potential for increased levels of stress is apparent from pressures for change occurring in the contemporary work environment (Cooper, 2005; Noblet, Rodwell, & Allisey, 2009; Schabracq & Cooper, 2000). For instance, productivity pressures, short-term contract culture of employment, job uncertainties due to corporate restructuring, increase in the pace, volume, and complexity of workloads faced by employees, outsourcing of operations, growing international competition, changes in organisational strategies, and rapid social modernisation in work styles have generated unprecedented levels of stress in organisations (see Moncrief et al., 1997; Noblet & Rodwell, 2008). Stress experienced at work can have adverse outcomes for health, well-being and morale of individual employees (Antoniou, Davidson, & Cooper, 2003; Cooper & Cartwright, 1994) and contributes to a significant portion of worker compensation claims, health-care costs, disability, absenteeism, and productivity losses

(Murphy, 1995). As work plays a central role in the lives of many people, the impact of job stress is an important issue both for individual employees and the organisations in which they work (Bradley & Sutherland, 1994; Le Fevre, Kolt, & Matheny, 2006). Therefore, only by better understanding sources and issues surrounded by job stress academics and practitioners can contribute in terms of coping strategies and policies to deal with the costly effects of stress, mental ill health and lack of well-being.

Researchers have dealt with various issues of job stress and have accumulated a substantial and consistent body of research literature (e.g. Cooper & Marshall, 1976; Johnson et al., 2005; Lu et al., 2003; Murphy, 1995; Stowell, Tumminaro, & Attarwala, 2008). However, scholars suggest that the causes and effects of job stress remain poorly understood (see Dewe & Guest, 1990; Newton, 1989; Siu, Lu, & Cooper, 1999). It is said that the success of any effort to reduce job stress will depend on accurate diagnosis as different stressors require different actions (see Fulcheri et al., 1995). This implies the need of research that focused on evaluating different coping strategies to find out which strategies are effective on job stress (see Bradley & Sutherland, 1994; Le Fevre et al., 2006; van der Hek & Plomp, 1997). However, scholars have highlighted the need of investigating not only the general effectiveness of interventions but also the importance of investigating moderation effects (see Norcross, 2001). On one hand, if moderators are ignored in treatment studies, participants may be given a treatment that is inappropriate or perhaps even harmful for them (Kraemer et al., 2001). On the other, the identification of important moderation effects indicates the maturity and sophistication of a field of inquiry (see Aguinis, Boik & Pierce, 2001; Judd, McClelland & Culhane, 1995). In this context, the specific aim of this paper is to examine the moderating effect of coping strategies on the relationship between work-related dimensions (i.e., work routinization, role clarity, relationships with others, and promotional opportunity) and job stress using quantitative methodology.

When it comes to addressing stress at workplace, some scholars suggest that though individual level coping strategies seem to be the most commonly adopted approach in practice more broadly focused organisational approaches should be the interventions of choice (see

Cousins et al., 2004). Some other scholars highlight the importance of addressing coping at the level of the individual otherwise well-proven individual level strategies may be inappropriately relegated (see Le Fevre et al., 2006 p.562). However, very little evidence available on which to base the organisational focused stress management strategies and little clear information on the relative effectiveness of various coping strategies in general (see Dewe, 2003; Ho, 1997; Le Fevre et al., 2006). Therefore, the current study explores the views of individuals on the usage of both individual-based and organisation-based coping strategies in mitigating job stress to provide some useful empirical evidence that could be used in introducing coping strategies and policies that can make a difference.

In the above context, by taking into account how work-related antecedents affect job stress and how coping strategies influence the relationship, the study tested the role of coping strategies as a moderator between work-related dimensions and job stress of white collar employees in the private sector of Sri Lanka. It is expected that this article will provide empirical evidence as the basis for planning future stress coping strategies. In order to provide the context for the article, in the next section, relevant literature is briefly reviewed. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The article concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Theoretical background and hypotheses

Job stress and sources of job stress

Job stress is generally defined in literature as an employee's feeling of job-related hardness, tension, anxiety, frustration, worry, emotional exhaustion and distress (Armstrong & Griffin, 2004). In other words, work-related variables (job stressors), when interpreted by the individual (cognitive interpretation), may lead to stress (Dua, 1994). Therefore, stressors denote the external force or situation acting on the individual - objective events. Stress denotes the deformation or changes produced in the individual as a result of those forces - subjective experience of the event (Le Fevre, Matheny, & Kolt, 2003).

A number of aspects of working life have been identified as linked to stress (see for example Burke, 1988; Cropanzano et al., 1997; Gold, Park & Punnett, 2006; Noblet & Rodwell, 2008; Noblet et al., 2009; Perrewe & Ganster, 1989; Yang, Che & Spector, 2008). For instance, role-based factors such as the lack of power, role ambiguity, and role conflict (e.g. Burke, 1988; Nelson & Burke, 2000); threats to career development and achievement such as the threat of redundancy, being undervalued, and unclear promotion prospects (e.g. Nelson & Burke, 2000; Yang et al., 2008); the quality of the social environment in the workplace including relationships with others (e.g. Cooper & Marshall, 1976; Noblet & Rodwell, 2008; Sparks & Cooper, 1999; Yang et al., 2008), and task uncertainty and task content (e.g. Gold et al., 2006; Nelson & Burke, 2000) have been frequently identified as stressors.

The current study is confined to examine the effects of four work-related stressors in creating a feeling of stress in individuals, i.e., promotional opportunity, role clarity, work routinization, and relationships with others (co-workers and the immediate supervisor). Of these four stressors, promotional opportunity could be identified as a stressor related to organisational practices, role clarity and work routinization could be identified as stressors related to job/task features, and relationships with others could be identified as a stressor related to helping relationships that come from co-workers and the immediate supervisor.

First, work routinization is the degree to which a job is repetitive (Price & Mueller 1986, p. 11 cited in Price, 1997, p 522). A high degree of repetitiveness signifies a highly routinized job (Price, 1997). As work routinization is based on the nature of the tasks performed by an individual worker, scholars identify work routinization under a diversity of labels, such as task variety, task variability, formatted tasks, task predictability, uncertainty, and work-flow predictability (see Gold et al., 2006; Price, 1997). Extant literature suggests two extreme ends in the continuum of the level of work 'routineness'. The one end is where work is performed regularly and contains no or few variable work elements, so that the frequency of occurrence, total work cycle (duration) and content (sequence of elements) all vary little or not at all. The other end is where there is no easily defined work cycle at all and the worker's activity cannot

readily be predicted for any given point in time or there is very high variability in work element frequency, duration or content (Gold et al., 2006, p. 14). Second, the lack of helping relationships that come from co-workers and the immediate supervisor has also been identified as a source of job stress and lack of employees' well-being at work (e.g. Burke 1988; Cooper & Marshall 1976; Noblet & Rodwell, 2008; Yang et al., 2008). Extant literature suggests that strain felt by employees increase when the demands of a job situation are not matched by adequate levels of support from supervisors and colleagues (Noblet & Rodwell, 2008; Yang et al., 2008). Consistent with past research, hypothesis proposed for this study is composite:

Hypothesis 1. (a) Work routinization and (b) the lack of promotional opportunity will be positively related to job stress.

Third, role clarity is the degree to which individuals perceive that required information is provided about how the employee is expected to perform his or her job (Teas, Walker, & Hughes, 1979). Literature identifies the lack of clarity about role expectations as role ambiguity (see Price, 1997), where Rizzo, House and Lirtzman (1970) define role ambiguity as relating to an individual who lacks clear direction about the expectations of his or her role in the job or organisation. Hence, role ambiguity arises when individuals do not have a clear picture about their work objectives, their co-workers' expectation of them, and the scope and responsibilities of their jobs. Several previous research identified the lack of clarity about the job as an important antecedents to job stress (e.g. Burke, 1988; Nelson & Burke, 2000; Netemeyer, Johnston, & Burton, 1990). Finally, the lack of opportunities for advancement, which individuals being dependent upon their performance, is identified as an important antecedent to job stress (e.g. Cooper & Marshall, 1976; Nelson & Burke, 2000). Previous studies have demonstrated a link of opportunities for advancement with employees' mental and physical well-being, where employees with high level of opportunities for advancement demonstrate high psychological and physical well-being (Yang et al., 2008). Consistent with past research, hypothesis proposed for this study is composite:

Hypothesis 2. (a) Role clarity and (b) the existence of helping relationships with others (co-workers and the immediate supervisor) will be negatively related to job stress.

Coping strategies

Stress management interventions are defined as “any purposeful actions taken to reduce or alleviate the stress experienced by organisational citizens in the execution of their work functions” (Le Fevre et al., 2006 p. 548). According to Le Fevre et al. (2006) this broad definition excludes all those actions whose primary purpose is other than the management of stress but which may, nevertheless, have impact on it. Adapting from the above definition, for the current study coping strategies are identified as actions or initiatives that have been preferably used by organisational citizens to reduce or alleviate the stress experienced by them in the execution of their work functions.

The review of extant literature suggests that initiatives that can be used to reduce or alleviate job stress can be classified as primary, secondary, and tertiary (see Quick et al., 1997). Primary initiatives are aimed to deal with the sources of stress in the workplace by means of, for instance, job design, organisational restructuring, and organisational development initiatives (De Frank & Cooper, 1987, van der Hek & Plomp, 1997; van der Klink et al., 2001). Extant literature classifies secondary initiatives into three main types- somatic, cognitive, and multimodal (see Le Fevre et al., 2006). Somatic approaches include relaxation methods such as breathing techniques; cognitive approaches include methods such as mindfulness techniques; multimodal approaches combine aspects of both somatic and cognitive methods such as relaxation response and transcendental meditation (see Le Fevre et al., 2006). Tertiary initiatives concerned with the treatment of manifested symptomatic disease (physical or psychological) in affected individuals by the provision of medical/psychiatric care, counselling, or employee assistance programmes (De Frank & Cooper, 1987; Quick et al., 1997; van der Hek & Plomp, 1997). This Quick et al.’s (1997) classification approximately equates to De Frank and Cooper’s (1987) typology of individual,

individual/organisational, or organisational approaches, where secondary initiatives correspond to De Frank and Cooper's (1987) individual-based initiatives while primary initiatives corresponds to individual/organisational and organisational initiatives. Further, it is suggested that initiatives such as employee assistance programmes included under individual initiatives may be better classified as tertiary by Quick's schema (see Le Fevre et al., 2006). However, as mentioned earlier, the current study concentrates on strategies used by individuals to better cope with job stress and these strategies may include both secondary as well as tertiary initiatives. In this regard, extant literature also suggests that secondary and tertiary level initiatives are commonly employed in organisations than primary initiatives (see Barkham & Shapiro, 1990; Le Fevre et al., 2006).

With regard to individuals' use of coping strategies Cooper, Sloan, & Williams (1988) classify these into six sub-scales, i.e., social support, task strategies, logic, home-work relationship, hobbies and outside interests, time management, and involvement. Some other researchers classify coping strategies into problem-focused and emotion-focused (see Carver, Scheier, & Weintraub, 1989; Voight, 2009). Problem-focused coping strategies are used to alter the source of the stressor, for instance, seeking instrumental support, problem solving, planning, and increased effort (Voight, 2009). Emotion-focused coping are strategies used to reduce the emotional distress associated with a stressful situation, for instance, seeking social support, behavioural withdrawal, and wishful thinking (Voight, 2009). He, Zhao and Archbold (2002) and McCarty, Zhao and Garland (2007) classify individual level coping strategies into two, i.e., positive or constructive coping and negative or destructive coping. Constructive coping strategies are direct, positive, and adaptive responses to work-related stress such as communication with spouse (McCarty et al., 2007). Destructive coping strategies are negative and avoidance techniques used to deal with work-related stress such as getting isolated from friends or family members (He et al., 2002).

With regard to the treatment of coping strategies in the previous research studies, several research studies treated coping strategies as an independent variable (e.g. He et al., 2002; Kirkcaldy, Brown, & Cooper, 1998; McCarty et al., 2007; Young & Cooper, 1995); few

research studies treated coping strategies as a moderator variable (e.g. Chen et al., 2009; Murphy, 1995; Stowell et al., 2008). The current study treats individuals' usage of coping strategies as a moderator, where different coping strategies used by individuals operate to strengthen/weaken the relationship between work-related dimensions and job stress.

Therefore, the hypotheses proposed for this study are composites:

Hypothesis 3. Coping strategies moderate the positive relationship between (a) work routinization and (b) the lack of promotional opportunity and job stress in such a way that the influence on job stress will be weakened for higher than for lower levels of the usage of coping strategies.

Hypothesis 4. Coping strategies moderate the negative relationship between (a) role clarity and (b) the existence of helping relationships with others (co-workers and the immediate supervisor) and job stress in such a way that the influence on job stress will be strengthened for higher than for lower levels of the usage of coping strategies.

Method

Sample

The target population for the study is a broad cross-section of full-time white-collar employees in the private sector organisations located in Colombo, which is considered as the main commercial and financial hub of Sri Lanka. The preliminary investigations made prior to data collection led to suggest that formal initiatives for stress management is more likely to be available in medium to large scale organisations. Therefore, three available directories, i.e., Colombo Stock Exchange, the Registrar of Companies, and business section of the Sri Lanka Telecom Telephone Directory were used to identify possible organisations belong to different industries having 150 or more employees. With the help of the directories, a random sample of 180 organisations was selected. To distribute the self-administered survey questionnaire across selected organisations, contact persons were identified through commercial and

financial associations, employees' welfare associations or trade unions, educational programmes offered for white-collar employees by educational institutes, and personal networks. The contact persons distributed the survey questionnaire among a heterogeneous sample of white-collar employees full-time employed and ranked at different levels within the organisations. Of the 600 self-administered questionnaires sent out, 385 completed questionnaires returned within 4 weeks of initial distribution during January to December 2008. This yielded a response rate of 64 percent. The characteristics of the sample are shown in Table I.

Take in Table I

Measures

Unless otherwise stated, all constructs were measured using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). For all measurement scales, standardised Cronbach's alpha was examined and Principal-components factor analysis (Varimax rotation) was conducted. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7 (see Hair et al., 1999), The items of each factor were averaged to produce a mean score for the each construct (refer to Table III).

Dependent variable. Job stress was measured using five items from Lambert et al., (2006). Example items include "A lot of time my job makes me very frustrated or angry" and "I am usually under a lot of pressure when I am at work". The higher number indicates a higher level of job stress. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha=.78; Eigenvalue=2.40; Explained variation=60.03%.

Moderating variable. The list of coping strategies that can be used by individuals was generated from preliminary inquiries made during the study and from the review of the existing literature (such as Bradley & Sutherland, 1994; He et al., 2002; Le Fevre et al., 2006; Kitaoka-Higashiguchi et al., 2003; McCarty et al., 2007; O'Connor & Shimizu, 2002; Voight, 2009). Respondents were also given the opportunity to mention other strategies they used that are not included in the list. Respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they use each strategy using a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 (do not use) to 5 (use a great deal).

In analysing the responses for coping strategies, a frequency distribution was produced to check on the strategies used. The results are shown in Appendix 1. Analysis showed that 17-item measure had standardised Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.83. Two items were eliminated as their score correlation sums were less than 0.4 (see Brace, Kemp, & Snelgar, 2006). These two items were "I have to slowdown my work" and "I re-structured my family and social life". The remaining 15-item measure retained a reliability of 0.90. Principal-components factor analysis yielded a set of four factors, which explained 70 per cent (69.87) of the variance. Of these four factors, Factor 1 was labelled as "Individual positive coping", Factor 2 as "Workplace initiatives", Factor 3 as "Workplace informal support", and Factor 4 as "Individual destructive coping". The first three factors could also be identified under the umbrella term "Constructive coping methods". Table II summarises the results of the factor analysis.

Take in Table II

Independent variables. Work routinization, the degree to which the job is repetitive, was measured by five items adapted from Price and Mueller (1986, p. 11 cited in Price, 1997, p 522). Example items include "My job requires me to do the same things over and over again" and "No creativity is required in my job". The higher number indicates a higher level of work

routinization. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha =.80; Eigenvalue=2.15; Explained variation=71.49%.

Role clarity was measured using items from Rizzo et al. (1970). Example items include "I know exactly what is expected of me in my job" and "I know what my responsibilities are". The higher number indicates a higher level of role clarity. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha=.67; Eigenvalue=1.50; Explained variation=75.21%.

Relationships with others (immediate supervisor and co-workers) was measured using six items from Price (1997). Example items include "My immediate supervisor is willing to listen to my job-related problems", "My immediate supervisor shows a lot of concern for me on my job", and "I am very friendly with one or more of my co-workers". The higher number indicates a higher level helping relationships. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha=.78; Eigenvalue=2.09; Explained variation=69.59%.

Promotional opportunity, i.e., the movement between different status levels within an organisation, was measured using six items from Iverson and Roy (1994). Example items include "Promotions are infrequent" and "Promotions are very rare". The higher number indicates a lower level of promotional opportunity. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where standardised Cronbach's alpha=.79; Eigenvalue=1.65; Explained variation=82.62%.

Control variables. The literature suggests that the extent to which job stress affects associated outcomes may vary depending upon an individual's demographic characteristics. For example, individual differences in terms of gender (e.g. Antoniou et al., 2003), age (e.g. Antoniou et al., 2003), education level (e.g. Kirkcaldy & Furnham, 1999), marital status (e.g. Kirkcaldy & Furnham, 1999), and tenure (e.g. Kirkcaldy & Furnham, 1999). Therefore, five individual demographic characteristics were controlled in the analysis. These variables are gender (female=0, male=1), marital status (single=0, married=1), age (continuous scale), the highest level of education (without a degree =0, with a degree=1), and the years of experience in the present workplace (continuous scale).

The questionnaire was originally developed in English and then it was translated into the native language, *Sinhala*, and finally translated back from *Sinhala* to English. The translated questionnaire was piloted with a random sample of people that fit with the intended sample of the study prior to the distribution.

Data analysis procedure

Hierarchical regression analysis was used to test the moderation hypotheses (see Frazier, Tix, & Barron, 2004). The variables were mean centred to increase interpretability of interactions (see Fraizer et al., 2004). The variables were entered into the regression equation in four steps. The control variables were entered in the first step, the independent variable was added in the second step, the moderator variables were added in the third step, and the interaction terms obtained by multiplying each moderator variable by the independent variable were added in the fourth step (see Fraizer et al., 2004). The plots were constructed by plotting low, medium and high scores on the perception of job stress and the variables that showed significant moderation in the hierarchical regression analysis. For this, Jose's (2002) Excel version of ModGraph programme was used. Following the recommendations of Aiken and West (1991), simple effects tests were conducted to determine whether the slopes differed significantly from zero.

Results

Table III shows means, standard deviations and zero-order correlations among the variables.

Take in Table III

A series of multiple regression analysis was conducted to test the moderator effect of coping strategies. First, control variables were regressed on the outcome variable. The results are shown in Tables IV (Model 1). Second, the effect of the four work-related dimensions on job stress was analysed. As shown in Table IV (Model 2), work routinization ($p < .001$) and lack of

promotional opportunity ($p < .05$) are significantly positively related to job stress. This supports Hypothesis 1. The existence of helping relationships (with co-workers and the immediate supervisor) ($p < .01$) and role clarity ($p < .05$) are significantly negatively related to job stress. This supports Hypothesis 2.

Take in Table IV

As the third step, the four components of coping strategies were entered into the model. As shown in Table IV (Model 3), individual positive coping ($p < .001$), workplace initiatives ($p < .001$), workplace informal support ($p < .05$), and individual destructive coping ($p < .05$) significantly impact on job stress.

Finally, interaction terms were entered into the model to test the moderating effect. Hypothesis 4(b) predicted that the relationship between “relationships with others” and job stress would be moderated by coping strategies. As indicated by the significant interaction terms in Table IV (Model 4), coping strategy “individual positive coping” and “workplace initiatives” moderated the relationship between “relationships with others” and job stress. Plots that illustrate the significant moderations are displayed in Figure 1. The plots were constructed by plotting low, medium and high scores of the variables as detailed in the section on data analysis procedure. Following the recommendations of Aiken and West (1991), simple effects tests were conducted to determine whether the slopes differed significantly from zero. These tests revealed that the relationship between “relationships with others” and job stress is moderated for high ($t = 2.12, p < .05$) and medium ($t = 2.14, p < .05$) levels of individual positive coping and was significantly different from zero (refer Figure 1a). Further, the relationship between “relationships with others” and job stress is also moderated for high ($t = 2.45, p < .001$), medium ($t = 3.73, p < .001$), and low ($t = 3.38, p < .001$) levels of workplace initiatives and was significantly different from zero (refer Figure 1b). However, the other two coping strategies of workplace informal support and individual destructive coping have not moderated the

relationship between “relationships with others” and job stress. Further, none of the coping strategies have moderated the relationships between job stress and work routinization, promotional opportunity, and role clarity as predicted by Hypotheses 3(a), 3(b) and 4(a).

Discussion and implications

The article presented findings of a study that investigated the associations between four work-related dimensions, job stress and coping strategies. Though a substantial and consistent body of research literature is accumulated on job stress few studies have investigated the role of coping strategies on the relationship between work-related dimensions and job stress. When individuals are faced with a range of possible coping strategies to deal with job stress, an evaluation of individuals’ use of coping strategies is required in making informed decisions in tackling the issues surrounded by job stress within a particular organisation.

The study tested a job specific model of stress depicting general relationships of sources of job stress rather than examining relationships existing in specific or unique job contexts. Further, existing well accepted multiple parameter scales have been used to gather data. The validation of a measure requires the assessment of measurement properties over a variety of samples in similar and different contexts. All the measures were shown to be valid and reliable in the Sri Lankan context.

As anticipated, it was found that the four work-related dimensions, i.e., work routinization, role clarity, relationships with others, and promotional opportunity have direct significant effects on job stress. This supports the findings of previous studies that were reviewed earlier. With regard to coping strategies, the mean values (refer to Appendix 1) for the usage of each coping strategy suggested that self-initiated strategies and help received from family members could be identified as highly used coping strategies. These were followed by help received from workplace colleagues and the immediate supervisor. The usage of recreational facilities provided by the workplace is also ranked as one of the main coping strategies. The factor analysis yielded four broad coping strategies that individuals use.

The prime objective of the study is to investigate whether coping strategies used by individuals moderate the relationship between work-related dimensions and job stress. It was found that both individual positive coping and workplace initiatives moderate the relationship between “relationships with others” and job stress. However, the other two coping strategies, i.e., workplace informal support and individual destructive coping, have not moderated the relationship between “relationships with others” and job stress. Further, none of the coping strategies (individual positive coping, workplace initiatives, workplace informal support, and individual destructive coping) have moderated the relationship between job stress and work-related dimensions of work routinization, role clarity, and promotional opportunity. This implies that different stressors require different actions. Therefore, an understanding of the impact of different coping strategies may help to arrive at suggestions of ways of addressing job stress.

The study confined to investigate both secondary as well as tertiary strategies used by individuals to better cope with job stress. The findings suggest that the impact on job stress from the three sources of stress (work routinization, role clarity, and promotional opportunity) was not influenced by the coping strategies investigated in this study. Therefore, it could be assumed that the individual usage of available stress coping strategies may not be effective as a reactive strategy in the removal of these stressors. However, exploring the possible importance of primary mechanisms as a proactive strategy to remove the stressors of work routinization, the lack of role clarity, and the lack of promotional opportunity was beyond the scope of this study.

Limitations and future research

This study was designed as a cross-sectional study employing quantitative methodology. 385 full-time white-collar employees in the private sector organisations responded to the survey questionnaire. As information about non-respondents to the survey questionnaire has not been recoded, it is difficult to know whether respondents differ from non-respondents. Though several steps, as discussed earlier, were taken to recruit as far as possible a heterogeneous sample, the size of the sample is small compared to previous studies conducted in the area of

stress. Further, though one can envisage a wide range of sources of stress within the work environment, the current study was confined to investigate four work-related dimensions. Furthermore, there could be other organisational factors that could influence work-related dimensions explored in the study. For example, the nature of management (e.g. poor management) could sour relationships with others. Future studies could explore the influence of such factors. In addition, previous research (such as Antoniou et al., 2003) suggests that all individuals will not perceive the same situation as stressful and the individual differences they bring along with them (such as gender and personality) could influence an individual's responses to job stress. However, the current study has not specifically explored such differences. The sample of the study has been pooled from various private sector organisations. In this regard, one could argue that a particular workplace factor may not consistently relate to stress in all workplaces. Hence, future research could confine their samples, for instance, to a particular industry or profession. In addition, future studies could explore the possible importance of organisation led primary mechanisms in addressing job stress. Further, the findings suggest that individuals use recreational facilities provided by the workplace as a coping strategy to reduce stress. Hence, future studies could inquire into organisational views on actual reasons behind the introduction of such initiatives, in other words, whether those were intended to function in the capacity of stress reduction.

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Figure

Figure 1: Moderation effects- relationships with others moderated by individual positive coping and workplace initiatives.

Tables

Table I: Characteristics of the sample

<i>Specialised area of work:</i>		<i>Age:</i>	
Technical (e.g. engineering, IT, production, and scientific in nature)	36%	Less than 35 years	33%
Accounting and financial	20%	35-50 years	58%
Marketing	22%	Over 50 years	9%
General Administration	22%	<i>Work experience:</i>	
		Less than 5 years	33%
<i>Gender:</i>		5-10	44%
Male	72%	Over 10 years	23%
Female	28%	<i>Highest level of education:</i>	
<i>Marital status:</i>		With out a degree	39%
Married	56%	With a degree (bachelor's or postgraduate degree)	61%
Single	44%		

Table II: Summarised results: coping strategies

	Constructive coping			F4:
	F1: Individual positive coping	F2: Workplace initiatives	F3: Workplace informal support	Individual destructive coping
I follow self-techniques (such as listening to music) to relax while I am working	.70	-	-	-
I talk to my spouse/family members about issues at work.	.64	-	-	-
I exercise regularly to reduce tension.	.64	-	-	-
I seek special assistance from counsellors/medical care.	.67	-	-	-
I undertake spiritual/meditation programmes.	.61	-	-	-
I use recreational facilities provided by the workplace.	-	.59	-	-
Stress management training is provided by the workplace.	-	.72	-	-
Workplace provides health and fitness programmes.	-	.70	-	-
Workplace provides spiritual/meditation programmes.	-	.74	-	-
I seek advice from superiors to re-organise my daily workload.	-	-	.88	-
My colleagues at work help me to overcome tension at work.	-	-	.87	-
I stay away from every one as I want to be alone.	-	-	-	.64
I smoke more to help me relax.	-	-	-	.63
I let my feelings out by smashing things.	-	-	-	.79
I hangout more with my friends at bars/clubs.	-	-	-	.78
Explained variation	32.53%	21.86%	8.86%	6.62%
Eigenvalue	4.88	3.01	1.78	1.32
Standardised Cronbach's alpha	.75	.73	.79	.78

Table III: Correlations

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. Work routinization	3.87	0.76	1							
2. Role clarity	3.80	0.79	-.02	1						
3. Relationships with others	3.38	0.87	-.06	.47**	1					
4. Promotional opportunity	3.01	0.99	.42**	.30**	.22**	1				
5. Individual positive coping	3.52	0.74	.29**	.20**	.10	.46**	1			
6. Workplace initiatives	3.03	0.75	.29**	.03	.11	.42**	.46**	1		
7. Workplace informal support	2.88	1.01	.32**	.15*	.14*	.35**	.52**	.60**	1	
8. Individual destructive coping	1.82	0.75	.24**	.08	.22**	.29**	.40**	.53**	.37*	1
9. Job stress	3.60	1.10	.33**	-.35**	-.40**	.06	-.28**	-.23**	-.24*	-.28*

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table IV: Results of hierarchical regression analysis for job stress

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
<i>Step 1: Control</i>				
Age	.23**	.13*	.18*	.13*
Tenure	.08	.11	.10	.08
Education	-.39**	-.21**	-.14*	-.16*
Gender	-.15**	-.10	-.08	-.13*
Marital status	-.19**	-.15**	-.13	-.09
<i>Step 2: Independent</i>				
Work routinization		.28***	.24***	.31
Role clarity		-.15*	-.19**	-.25
Relationships with others		-.16**	-.13*	-.38***
Promotional opportunity		.09*	.12	.50**
<i>Step 3: Moderators</i>				
Individual positive coping			-.16**	-.40**
Workplace initiatives			-.15**	-.48**
Workplace informal support			-.09*	-.06
Individual destructive coping			-.10*	-.09
<i>Step 4: Interaction terms</i>				
Work routinization x Individual positive coping				-.27
Work routinization x Workplace initiatives				-.29
Work routinization x Workplace informal support				.18
Work routinization x Individual destructive coping				.18
Role clarity x Individual positive coping				-.27
Role clarity x Workplace initiatives				-.15
Role clarity x Workplace informal support				.22
Role clarity x Individual destructive coping				.19
Relationships with others x Individual positive coping				-.86***
Relationships with others x Workplace initiatives				-.74*
Relationships with others x Workplace informal support				-.28
Relationships with others x Individual destructive coping				-.20
Promotional opportunity x Individual positive coping				.18
Promotional opportunity x Workplace initiatives				.33
Promotional opportunity x Workplace informal support				-.22
Promotional opportunity x Individual destructive coping				.23
R ² (Adj.)	.28	.41	.44	.63
F change	-	21.46***	16.66***	16.31***
ΔR ²	-	.43***	.47***	.67***

* p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<.001

Standardised regression coefficients (betas) are reported.

Appendix 1: Descriptive analysis – coping strategies

	Mean	Std. Deviation
I follow self-techniques (such as listening to music) to relax while I am working	4.19	0.95
I talk to my spouse/family members about issues at work.	3.86	0.96
My colleagues at work help me to overcome tension at work.	3.30	1.19
I use recreational facilities provided by the workplace.	3.27	0.93
I seek advice from superiors to re-organise my daily workload.	3.26	1.12
I seek special assistance from counsellors/medical care.	2.97	1.22
I undertake spiritual/meditation programmes.	2.86	1.00
I exercise regularly to reduce tension.	2.76	1.20
Workplace provides health and fitness programmes.	2.21	1.23
I hangout more with my friends at bars/clubs.	1.90	1.10
I stay away from every one as I want to be alone.	1.87	0.98
Workplace provides spiritual/meditation programmes.	1.84	1.03
I smoke more to help me relax.	1.81	1.24
Stress management training is provided by the workplace.	1.79	1.02
I let my feelings out by smashing things.	1.69	0.95
I re-structured my family and social life.	1.60	1.35
I have to slowdown my work.	1.55	0.92